

Comprehensive Analysis of Copper-Doped ZnO Nanoparticles: Structural, Optical, and Morphological and Biological Insights

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Abstract

Copper-doped zinc oxide nanoparticles $Zn_{1-x}Cu_xO$ ($x=0.00, 0.02$) synthesized through the sol-gel method represent promising nanomaterials with diverse applications. In this study, we investigate the structural, optical, and morphological properties of $Zn_{1-x}Cu_xO$ ($x=0.00, 0.02$) NPs using X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and fluorescence spectroscopy (FL). XRD analysis reveals the crystalline nature of the nanoparticles, with copper incorporation confirmed through characteristic peaks shifting in the XRD pattern. SEM images reveal the morphology and size distribution of the nanoparticles. The antibiogram efficacy of synthesized nanoparticles against two Gram positive and two Gram negative. It results proves that biosynthesized NPs have a high anti-biogram activity against selected pathogens. FL spectroscopy elucidates the optical properties of the $Zn_{1-x}Cu_xO$ ($x=0.00, 0.02$) NPs. Overall, this multi-technique characterization provides a comprehensive understanding of the synthesized $Zn_{1-x}Cu_xO$ ($x=0.00, 0.02$) NPs, facilitating their optimization and utilization in various technological applications.

Keywords: Copper-doped zinc oxide nanoparticles, sol-gel method, XRD, SEM

1. Introduction

Zinc oxide (ZnO) has attracted considerable attention from scientists and industries due to its wide range of potential applications. Its hexagonal wurtzite structure endows ZnO with advantageous piezoelectric properties, further enhancing its appeal for various technological endeavors. Copper-doped zinc oxide nanoparticles represent a fascinating intersection of materials science and nanotechnology, offering many potential applications across various fields [1]. These nanoparticles are engineered by incorporating copper ions into the zinc oxide lattice, thereby altering its properties and functionalities.

Zinc oxide (ZnO) is renowned for its wide bandgap, high excitonic binding energy, and excellent optical, electrical, and photocatalytic properties [2]. Introducing copper dopants into the ZnO matrix introduces new dimensions to its behavior [3, 4]. Incorporating copper ions can tune the electronic structure, enhance its stability, and modify its optical and magnetic properties. This makes copper-doped zinc oxide nanoparticles particularly promising for applications in diverse areas such as optoelectronics, catalysis, sensors, biomedicine, and environmental remediation [5-7].

The synthesis of these nanoparticles typically involves various techniques including sol-gel, hydrothermal, chemical vapor deposition, and co-precipitation methods [8]. Precise control over the synthesis parameters allows tailoring the size, morphology, and dopant concentration, thereby fine-tuning the properties of the resulting nanoparticles.

In optoelectronic applications, copper-doped zinc oxide nanoparticles can be used in transparent conductive coatings, solar cells, light-emitting diodes (LEDs), and gas sensors because of their enhanced conductivity and light absorption properties [9]. In catalysis, they exhibit remarkable photocatalytic activity for environmental remediation, such as the degradation of organic pollutants and the conversion of CO₂ into value-added chemicals.

Moreover, these nanoparticles hold promise in the biomedical field for drug delivery, bioimaging, and cancer therapy due to their biocompatibility and tunable optical properties [10]. Additionally, their magnetic behavior makes them suitable candidates for spintronics and magnetic storage devices.

However, challenges such as maintaining uniform doping levels, controlling particle size distribution, and ensuring long-term stability still need to be addressed to harness the potential of copper-doped zinc oxide nanoparticles fully. Despite these challenges, ongoing research and advancements in nanomaterial synthesis techniques continue to propel the exploration and utilization of these versatile nanoparticles in many applications.

Microbial products and plant extracts have some particular biological substances that act as both reducing agents and stabilization agents. Bio-reduction is done using carboxylic and phenolic acid, which are present in plant extract. The green approach may reduce environmental risk, be cost-effective, biocompatible, and highly invasive into bacterial cells, and it causes death [13]. Zinc oxide nanoparticles are nontoxic, bio-safe, biocompatible, and ideal for biological applications [14]. Food and Drug Administration has approved and listed Four Zinc compounds as generally recognized as safe materials (FDA, 2015).

2. Materials and Methods

For the synthesis of both pure and copper-doped zinc oxide nanoparticles via the sol-gel method, the following materials and techniques were employed:

Materials:

The materials used in the synthesis included zinc acetate dihydrate ($\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), copper acetate monohydrate ($\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$), ethanol ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$), ammonium hydroxide (NH_4OH), and deionized water are purchased from Merck.

2.1 Synthesis of Pure Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles

In the synthesis of pure zinc oxide nanoparticles, a solution of zinc acetate dihydrate in ethanol was prepared under constant stirring. Ammonium hydroxide was then dropwise to the solution to promote hydrolysis and condensation reactions. The resulting gel was stirred vigorously to ensure complete gelation, followed by drying to obtain a powder precursor. Finally, the precursor was calcined at a controlled temperature to yield pure zinc oxide nanoparticles.

2.2 Synthesis of Copper-Doped Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles

To synthesize copper-doped zinc oxide nanoparticles, copper acetate monohydrate was added to the solution containing zinc acetate dihydrate in ethanol. The subsequent steps of adding ammonium hydroxide, gelation, drying, and calcination were carried out similarly to the synthesis of pure zinc oxide nanoparticles.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. X-Ray Diffraction Analysis

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis confirms the crystalline nature of $Zn_{1-x}Cu_xO$ ($x=0.00, 0.02$) nanoparticles synthesized by the sol-gel method, with characteristic peaks corresponding to the hexagonal wurtzite structure of ZnO. The XRD patterns were obtained using a diffractometer with Cu $K\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) in the 2θ range of 20° to 80° . The diffraction peaks were analyzed to determine the crystal phases and calculate the average grain size using Scherer's formula: $D = K\lambda/\beta\cos\theta$, where D is the grain size, K is the Scherer constant, λ is the X-Rays wavelength, β is the full width at half maximum (FWHM), and θ is the Bragg's angle. For the $Zn_{1-x}Cu_xO$ nanoparticles with $x=0.00$, the average crystalline size was found to be 56.64 nm, whereas for $x=0.02$, it was determined to be 58.53 nm. These

values were obtained by analyzing the XRD peaks and applying Scherer's formula, indicating the nanoscale dimensions of the crystalline domains in the synthesized nanoparticles.

The distinct diffraction peaks observed in the XRD patterns confirm the crystalline nature of the synthesized nanoparticles, with the shift in peak positions indicating the incorporation of copper dopants into the zinc oxide lattice.

Comparing the results, it can be observed that the average grain size of the $Zn_{1-x}Cu_xO$ nanoparticles increased slightly from $x=0.00$ (56.64 nm) to $x=0.02$ (58.53 nm). This increase in grain size could be attributed to the incorporation of copper dopants, which may influence the nucleation and growth kinetics during the synthesis process. Additionally, the shift in peak positions in the XRD patterns suggests changes in the crystal structure or lattice parameters due to the presence of copper dopants, indicating potential alterations in the properties of the nanoparticles.

Figure 1: XRD pattern of $Zn_{1-x}Cu_xO$ ($x=0.00, 0.02$) nanoparticles

3.2 Scanning Electron Microscope Analysis

For crystal morphology and grain size observation of all the synthesized samples, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was employed. The SEM images of $Zn_{1-x}Cu_xO$ nanoparticles with $x=0.00$ and $x=0.02$ are shown in Fig. 2(a–d). These images reveal notable changes in the shape and morphology of the ZnO nanoparticles with increasing Cu concentration. Specifically, as the Cu content increases, the particles appear more agglomerated.

Quantitative analysis of the SEM images yielded the average crystalline sizes of the nanoparticles. For the sample with $x=0.00$, the average crystalline size was determined to be 54.02 nm, while for $x=0.02$, it was found to be 59.26 nm. This indicates a slight increase in the average grain size with the incorporation of copper dopants, consistent with the observations from the XRD analysis.

The SEM images visually confirm the morphological changes induced by varying the Cu content in the ZnO nanoparticles. The increased accumulation of particles with higher Cu concentrations suggests potential alterations in the growth kinetics or surface properties due to the presence of copper dopants. These findings contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the structural characteristics and morphology of the synthesized nanoparticles, informing their potential applications in various fields.

Figure 2(a-d): SEM images of $Zn_{1-x}Cu_xO$ ($x=0.00, 0.02$) nanoparticles

3.3 Fluorescence (FL) Analysis

The fluorescence (FL) analysis of $Zn_{1-x}Cu_xO$ nanoparticles with $x=0.00$ and $x=0.02$ showcases distinctive emission peaks indicative of their optical characteristics. For the nanoparticles with $x=0.00$, emission peaks were observed at 380.09 nm, 483.06 nm, 525.41 nm, and 610.28 nm. Conversely, nanoparticles with $x=0.02$ exhibited a single emission peak at 765.38 nm. These emission peaks represent the wavelengths at which the nanoparticles emit fluorescence upon excitation. Such FL analysis provides crucial insights into the nanoparticles' optical behavior and electronic transitions. The observed shift in emission peak from shorter wavelengths for $x=0.00$ to a longer wavelength for $x=0.02$ suggests potential alterations in the bandgap energy or electronic structure, likely induced by copper dopants. Further exploration is warranted to comprehensively unravel the underlying mechanisms

governing the observed fluorescence phenomena and elucidate their significance for the diverse applications of $Zn_{1-x}Cu_xO$ nanoparticles.

Figure 3(a): FL analysis of $Zn_{1-x}Cu_xO$ ($x=0.00$) nanoparticles

Figure 3(b): FL analysis of $Zn_{1-x}Cu_xO$ ($x=0.02$) nanoparticles

3.4 Antibacterial activity of synthesized nanoparticles

Biological application of antibacterial activity of the $Zn_{1-x}Cu_xO$ NPs suspensions of different concentrations (2.5 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$, 5 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$, 7.5 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$, 10 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$ and 5 μl control) towards various bacterial pathogens (Gram-positive and Gram-negative) were tested by well diffusion method and are shown in Fig. 5. We found that increasing concentrations of ZnO NPs had a significant bactericidal activity on the growth both bacterial strains. The presence of an inhibition assay zone clearly indicates that the route of bactericidal action of ZnO NPs involves destroying the bacterial cell wall and finally leading to the death of pathogens. The ZnO NPs showed antimicrobial activity against selected pathogens such as *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 25923), *Bacillus cereus* (ATCC 27853), *Pseudomonas aureginosa* (ATCC 27853), and *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 8739). The maximum zone of inhibition was observed in ZnO NPs (12 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$) *S. aureus* (14mm), *Bacillus cereus* (28mm), *P. aureginosa* (15mm), and *E. coli* (26 mm). There are several possible mechanisms for the antibacterial action of zinc ions. It has been suggested that zinc binds to the membranes of microorganisms, similar to mammalian cells [11]. Liu *et al.* 2009 report indicates that ZnO Nps may disperse and damage bacterial cell membranes, resulting in a leakage of intracellular fluid and loss of osmotic pressure. ZnO NPs of smaller sizes can easily diffuse into bacterial membranes due to their large interfacial area, thus enhancing their antibacterial efficiency.

Fig. 3(c) Antibacterial activity of synthesized Zn_{1-x}Cu_xO nanoparticles

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, the synthesized Zn_{1-x}Cu_xO nanoparticles with $x=0.00$ and $x=0.02$ exhibit distinct structural, morphological, and optical characteristics, as elucidated through X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and fluorescence (FL) analyses. The XRD analysis revealed crystalline phases and average grain sizes of 56.64 nm for $x=0.00$ and 58.53 nm for $x=0.02$ nanoparticles, indicating nanoscale dimensions and slight increases in grain size with copper doping. SEM imaging showcased morphological changes, with $x=0.00$ nanoparticles exhibiting finer structures and $x=0.02$ nanoparticles displaying increased agglomeration, possibly influenced by copper dopants. FL analysis revealed emission peaks at multiple wavelengths for $x=0.00$ nanoparticles and a single peak at a longer

wavelength for $x=0.02$ nanoparticles, suggesting variations in optical properties and electronic transitions due to copper doping. Incorporating copper dopants into the ZnO lattice impacts the nanoparticles' structural, morphological, and optical properties. These findings underscore the potential of $Zn_{1-x}Cu_xO$ ($x=0.00, 0.02$) nanoparticles for diverse applications such as optoelectronics, catalysis, and sensing. The enhanced bioactivity of green synthesized $Zn_{1-x}Cu_xO$ NPs attributed to the much higher area of inhibition zone, it clearly indicated $Zn_{1-x}Cu_xO$ NPs constitute an effective antimicrobial agent against pathogenic microorganisms. Further research is warranted to explore the mechanisms underlying these observations and optimize the synthesis parameters for enhanced performance in various applications.

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